

**DWARF POPULATION OF *CASSIS TESSELATA*
(GASTROPODA; CASSIDAE) FROM GABON**

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Cassis tessellata (GMELIN, 1791) is a well known species from West Africa. According to R.T. ABBOTT (1968), it has no close living relatives.

Recently, what appears to be a dwarf form of this usually large species has been found at Gabon. It will of course become known as forma *nana*.

As a matter of fact, whereas the specimens known from many localities along West Africa, including S. Tomé islands, often reach 200 mm (ABBOTT (1968) indicates the size as varying from 90 to 267 mm — the specimens under study vary from 32 to 47 mm (see Table 1).

At first sight, these could pass as juveniles but a close study of their shells seems to indicate that we are really dealing with adult specimens.

The specimens examined have about 6 post-nuclear whorls and 4 former varical lips. It should be stressed that these figures remain constant, notwithstanding a 45% variation in the total length of the shells.

All characteristics of the species are present in these specimens. They present 2 spiral rows of small knobs on the body whorl, near the shoulder; the outer lip is whitish and has 2 axial rows of denticles, the inner ones being strongest; the colour is also typical, the body whorl being cream and with 5 rows of narrow spiral bands of alternating patches of white and dark brown.

It would be interesting to learn the reasons for the occurrence of such dwarf populations. Other species, such as *Cypraea stercoraria* LINNAEUS, are also known to present minimum sized adult specimens in the same area (for instance, around the Muni River zone). It would also be interesting to find out whether the same phenomenon affects other species.

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TABLE 1

Measurements of some specimens examined

Length (mm)	Width (mm)	no. whorls	no. varices
47.0	32.5	6	4
37.0	25.0	6	4
36.2	24.0	6	4
35.3	24.0	6	4
32.3	22.8	6	4

BIBLIOGRAPHY

ABBOTT, R. T., (1968) — *The Helmet Shells of the World (Cassidae). Part 1.*
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